

Green Living Tour Program for Youth to Survive the Pandemic and in Support to Sustainable Living: A Case Study of Pohsanten Tourism Village in Bali Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 19, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 24, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Green Living, Tour program, Community-based tourism (CBT), CBT Product</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5725180</p>	<p><i>The aim of this study is to examine 'Green living tour program for the youth', an education tour program to promote a more sustainable way of living among the young generation, particularly a higher appreciation to forest. This is a qualitative study conducted through product trial or the experimentation of the existing Green Living Tour (GLT) by examining 9 aspects of tour assimilated from some tourism experts, which aspects consist of Duration, Timing, Variety of tourist attraction, The Strength of the attraction theme, Product delivery – guide, Food and Beverage, Transportation, Organisation and operation of the tour program, and Price. It was discovered that, for the tour program to have a higher impact wherein the participants experience a deep-dived green living, the central theme of 'green living' needs to be highlighted, strengthened and made as a focal point of the package by providing concept-internalisation, as well as the incorporation of a substantial content of green living practices in the tour program. The elimination of agro-cacao as the supporting theme of the tour is preferred. The modified version of Green Living Tour Program favoured by the Youth as the result of this research is subject to change, as adaptation is required to adjust with the shift of consumer's needs and preferences. The study output is a solution to two problems: firstly, protecting the forest by creating awareness and educating the Youth on sustainable living life style particularly related to forest; secondly, Community-based Tourism Pohsanten could survive the pandemic by offering product for local market.</i></p>

Introduction

Even though, many conservations projects and studies have been conducted on forest worldwide; yet, forest benefactors and activists are still not certain about the best solutions to save the forest and overcome the problems on hand (Newton, 2007). Nature, in this case forests are an integral part of human life system, and for the survival of the human race on Earth, forest must be looked after and conserved. Human's survival, growth, and wellbeing are relied upon the natural resources available around, these such as land, water, flora, fauna, microorganisms, minerals and energy (Sikor et al., 2010; William, 2010). The existence of forest, specifically the effectiveness of its function in supporting all aspects of living on the planet Earth are highly determined by the level of human's care and awareness of the importance of forests. Therefore, forest utilisation and management need to be well governed. Forest is one of the mediums for establishing a mutual relationship between humans and other living beings; regardless of the complexity of the ecological processes (Reksohadiprojo in Rahmawaty, 2004), and the prolonged conflict of interest among forest stakeholders (Voda, et al., 2017; Ernawati, et al., 2018); as forest sustainability is crucial, every effort to conserve forest is worth attempted. One of the important matters that factoring the achievement of a balance life-style on Earth is people's care for the natural environment without sacrificing economic and social welfare (Blowers, 1993). Moreover, in the field of tourism, tourists' engagement in activities related to ecological sustainability becomes an important factor contributing to a satisfying tourist experience (Ridho, Paisal, Mellita, & Roseno, 2021).

In comparison with the other regencies in Bali, Jembrana has the largest portion of forest area. The forest covers approximately 41.07% of the land (41,307 ha) (Forestry Statistic Department of Jembrana Regency, 2015). Currently, Jembrana regency that located in the Western part of Bali Island in Indonesia encounters a critical forest issue that concerns many people who care of the sustainability of the forest and living on Earth in general. The issue is triggered by the use of protected forest as an agricultural area, to cultivate crops such as banana, cacao and other type short-lived plants. This activity supports the life of the farmers economically, however has a huge potential hazard. In fact, due to the shift of forest function, some disasters have already occurred, these

for example: the volume shrinkage or even the dried out of river water which could cause the discontinuity of river ecosystem; soil erosion; flood that swept dwellings and crops alongside the river flow.

Humans should take the responsibility to restore the forest function, reduce and even stop all activities that threatening the ecosystem and life on the planet. None theless, a study conducted among the Youth in Jembrana Regency discovered that, a significant portion of the samples believes that the function of forest is mainly for economic benefit. As there is no clearly defined approach to solve the current issues related to forests (Newton, 2007), Ernawati, et.al. (2020) proposed to empower the Youth adopting green way of living as the best investment for making a change. The new generation adopting green lifestyle from the early stage will become a valuable benefactor to sustainable Earth. To extend the reach and increase the number of sustainable-conscious people particularly the local, Community-based Tourism Pohsanten (CBT Pohsanten) has adopted a strategy of forest restoration and tourism working in synergy. Promoting and creating awareness among the younger generation on green lifestyle start from shaping sustainable mindset by experiencing the Green Living Tour Program offered by Pohsanten Tourism Village (Figure 1). Moreover, sustainable future cannot be manifested without the input and participation of the Youth.

The green living tour program for the Youth is also expected to become a solution for CBT Pohsanten as a business entity. This tourist village located at Jembrana regency, initially aimed at catering international tourists by developing CBT products featuring authentic culture and the village environment. During Covid-19 pandemic, the Indonesian Government applies restriction to the international travels, the inflow of international tourist is yet uncertain. In order to keep operating, as a business entity CBT Pohsanten needs to develop a strategy by exploring the potential markets, their demands and needs; in which domestic market becomes a high viable option (Gurung, 2021), as 58.7% of the population prefers nature tourism (Yuni, 2020). This option could still become a feasible alternative even when the pandemic is over as tourism demand is fluctuating in nature, during low period, businesses are expected to be creative in order to fill the available capacity (Luciana and Sudiarta, 2019).

Figure 1. Green Living Class for the Youth

In respond to the situation, CBT Pohsanten opts to cater local market especially the Youth, simultaneously providing solution to the current issue of Jembrana regency. This article presents results of a study conducted through the product trial and the experimentation of the Existing Green Living Tour (Figure 2) that explore the solution devised by CBT Pohsanten in response to the issue of forest conservation in Jembrana regency, and also undertaking target market re-definition to survive the pandemic by developing and offering 'Green Living Tour Program for Youth'.

2. Sustainability and Tourism

The concept of sustainability was introduced in 1987 by the World Commission of Environment and Development (WCED), in a report entitled 'Our Common Future' (WCED, 1987). The concept was further developed highlighting sustainable development covering four areas (Parson et al., 1992), which include: Holistic planning; Preserving important ecological processes; The urgency to protect heritage and biodiversity; and Development should comprehend productivity as sustainability for the future generations.

The sustainability of the Earth's resources has become a massive issue (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2014). The major concerns include threats to biodiversity, specifically the extinction of vegetation and species, which will affect the ecosystem (Bio Diversity, 2010). The other critical issue is climate change (UN and Climate Change, 2014), and the accumulation of plastic waste in the oceans, for example, the Great Pacific Garbage Patch (Mother Nature Network, 2013). Many natural disasters occurred which were triggered by the Earth's current condition; thus, humans need to take affirmative actions and strive to conserve the planet, for species can continue inhabit the Earth.

In a broader sense sustainability is described as an outcome of a 'balance' or 'wise' use of resources (Lu and Nepal, 2009). They further claimed that the concept is understood, interpreted and implemented differently. In fostering sustainability WCED outlines sustainable development as the development that 'meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs' (United Nations General Assembly, 1987, p. 1). Nevertheless, a number of weaknesses were identified in relation to the principle. For instance, it is viewed as a single approach rather than a multiple approach (Wall, 1997), it lacks the discussion and anticipation of the complexity of human needs and the potential conflicts (Butler, 1999), and the tourism agenda is sometimes contradictory to sustainable development (Hunter, 1995).

Despite the number of unsustainable conducts, to some extent the world has practiced sustainability, for example: the ocean clean-up undertaken (The Ocean Cleanup, 2014); the Compact Mayors Coalition to reduce the energy related emissions (World Resources Institute, 2014); the certification of environmentally-friendly products, an initiative of certified sustainable tourists; the well implemented green human resources management at Alpina Hotel & Spa at Chamonix France gives significant benefits to people and the environment as well as increases the company profitability. At a local scope of Bali, this movement has also been initiated, this for example: the implementation of local sustainable concept of Tri Hita Karana within the corporate social responsibility activities at Grand Inna Kuta hotel in Bali (Bithara, Widana, & Murni, 2020); it is discovered that the implementation of green concept by the management of CauBelayu Tourism Village is still at the growing stage (Widana, & Sutarna, 2020); the management and operation model used at Omunitya traditional style accommodation in Bali Indonesia for the sustainability of the family heritage (Ernawati, N. M., Sitawati, A. A. R., Nadra, N. M., & Arjana, I W. B., 2020). This confirmed the argued that nowadays, more individuals, corporates and organisations participate in sustainable activities (Weaver, 2012; Buckley, 2012). Nonetheless, further actions are required to achieve significant impacts.

Many tourism academics foster sustainable living on Earth, for example, Weaver (2012) promotes environmentally-friendly corporate behaviour and products; Hall (2012) endorses 'voluntary simplicity' in life and promotes quality travel. Nowadays, 'sustainability' becomes popular and is used in many fields, including tourism (Choi and Sirakaya, 2005). Despite of Sustainable development being adopted to sustain the planet, yet, it is a great challenge to implement the concept (Lu & Nepal, 2009). Nevertheless, everyone should endeavour to participate in the movement within their field respectively. This research examined an endeavour made that make tourism and sustainability to operate in synergy for forest conservation, a Youth context.

3. Community-based Tourism Product

CBT is a type of alternative tourism that prioritizes local community participation during tourism development planning and operations, aims at the sustainability of local culture and environment, as well as improving the welfare of local communities; whilst, providing a satisfying CBT experience for tourists (Ernawati, 2018). Weaver (2006) explains that alternative tourism is the underpinning principle of CBT, that has become popular and used as a medium for community development (Singh, 2012; Telfer & Sharpley, 2008; Beeton, 2006). This movement is amplified by the fact that during the pandemic tourists predominantly (58.7%) choose nature tourism (Yuni, 2020).

Pohsanten Green Living Package
(Full Day for Class Package)
IDR 95,000 net/person

Rate Inclusions:

- Welcome morning coffee upon arrival at CBT Pohsanten Bali
- Trekking to rice field / Pohsanten river by our local guide
- 1 time Balinese Cuisine Lunch for 1 person
- 2 hour Green Living Class by our Speaker
- In the know to Agro Cacao by the Farmer
- 1 time Cokelat Senja at Agro Cacao for 1 person

Rate Conditions:

- The rate is quoted on a per package per person basis and in the net condition
- Above rate are valid for minimum 10 persons
- The activity of package could be customized / add on base on the requirement with additional surcharge

CBT Pohsanten Bali
Banjar Pasatan, Desa Pohsanten, Kecamatan Mendoyo, Kabupaten Jembrana, Bali, Indonesia 82281

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Figure 2.Existing Green Living Tour for Youth

Unlike business in general, CBT is a business entity owned by local communities in this context, the village; the attraction offered by CBT in the form of culture and nature is public property. It requires a sound management and the sharing of responsibilities, roles, participation, benefits and profits among CBT stakeholders. At Pohsanten village, CBT is not only aimed at providing an occupation option for the villagers, but also intended at providing an alternative solution to the current forest issue in the area of Jembrana regency in Bali province.

CBT is a form of Sustainable tourism which is also an Alternative tourism; the other features include: using ethnic culture of a community or the natural environment as tourist attractions; having a high level of local community participation in planning and management; minimising negative impacts on the local culture and environment; generating positive economic, environmental and socio-cultural impacts; providing rural tourism products that satisfy tourists. These reflect the features of quality destination, namely, outcome of a process that involved the suitability of all parties (UNWTO, n.d.). Further, the aspects of quality destinations according to the UNWTO include: perception of security, sanitation and health, respect for the environment and human heritage, resource and space planning, cleanliness, harmonious destination quality, connectivity, reasonable price, local hospitality, appropriate interpretation, enhanced accommodation and restaurant services, the sufficiency of infrastructure and public services. The minimum standard of eligibility to become a tourist destination includes the availability of tourist objects, access, accommodation, facilities, transportation, catering services, recreational activities, shopping, communication, banking systems, health, security, cleanliness, religious facilities, educational facilities and sports facilities (Kreck in Yoeti, 1996). The component of products offered in the village tourism is presented in Figure 3, which reflects the complexity of CBT products. The tourism village product scheme are structured from 4 broad categories: tourist attraction, the supporting services, supporting facilities, and the village and the community.

Quality tour/tour package contains these essential elements of attraction, transportation, accommodation, food beverage which is designed following principles such as the availability of dynamic and variations of tourist attractions and avoiding tight timing between activities (Gee, 1990). This research examined a tour program from 9 aspects, assimilated from the concepts developed by the previously mentioned sources as well as some additional aspects to suit the requirement of this study. Those aspects are presented in the research method section.

Figure 3. Tourism Village Product Scheme

4. Research Method

This research is a qualitative study using experimentation, direct participation, observation, and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) as data collecting methods. The respondents were asked to give feedback to their experience in participating/consuming the full day Green Living Tour packaged (leaflet in Figure 2 and 4). There were 3 groups participating the Green Living Tour program, and also 3 FGD were held, the respondents' profile is presented in Table 1. There were 3 experimentations conducted the first is an experiment on the initial Green Living Tour Program which is referred to as the 'Existing Green Living Tour Program' (Figure 2). The other two groups are the experiment on the refined Green Living Tour Program being referred to as 'Modified Green Living Tour' (Figure 4). The perception on the Existing Green Living Tour Program were also obtained from the observation to the previous groups participating the tour program.

The tour aspects examined in this Research were assimilated from the work of several experts which include: duration, timing, variety of attraction, food & beverage and transportation that adopted from (Gee, 1990); price from (UNWTO, n.d.); product delivery (Lothar A. Kreck in Yoeti 1996); and the other aspects: the strength of attraction theme, and organising package program were added for the purpose of this research, which made up of a total 9 aspects.

Figure 4. Modified Green Living Tour Brochure

One additional variable 'other inputs' was added as an open question to capture new idea. Thus, the 10 aspects comprise: 1) Duration, 2) Timing, 3) Variety of Tourist Attraction, 4) The Strength of the Attraction Theme, 5) Product delivery – Guide and Deliverer Component, 6) Food & Beverage, 7) Transportation, 8) Organizing program packages, 9) Price, 10) Other inputs.

Table 1.Profile of Respondents

Respondents	Gender		Education Background			Total
	Male	Female	Elementary	High School	Tertiary Education	
Tourism Student of PNB (Tour-Group 1)	15	10	-	-	25	25
Tourism Student of PNB (FGD-Group 1)	2	3	-	-	5	5
SD N 5 Pohsanten (Tour-Group 2)	4	4	8	-	-	8
SD N 5 Pohsanten (FGD-Group 2)	4	4	8	-	-	8
SD N 2 Pohsanten (Tour-Group 3)	5	2	7	-	-	7
SD N 2 Pohsanten (FGD-Group 3)	5	2	7	-	-	7
Total						60

The results of data collection from the experimentation on the 'Existing Green Living Tour' were analysed and compared with the results of the experimentation on the 'Modified Green Living tour', thus the Recommended Green Living Product of CBT Pohsanten for the Youth is formulated.

5.Results and Discussions

The results are separated into 2 sections: the experimentation results on the Existing Green Living Tour (GLT) and the results of Modified GLT. The brochure of the ModifiedGLT is presented in Figure 4.

5.1.Results and Discussion of Existing Green Living Tour

The result of one experiment group participating the existing tour is supplement by the perception of participants experiencing the same tour conducted earlier. The summary of the observation results is presented in Table 2, and the FGD Results is in Table 3.

Table 2. Observation Results - Existing Green Living

No	Aspect	Result
1	Duration	The trekking route is quite long and tiring, once the participants reach the terminating point at Pura Pasatan (Pasatan Temple) they cannot enjoy the view.
2	Timing	Activities sequence and timing are already in according to the rundown
3	Variety of Tourist	Sufficient: There are Green living class, Breeze walk for nice view,

	Attraction	cacao agro farming
4	The Strength of the Attraction Theme	Green living activity is sufficient but needs to be strengthened, related to the use of green materials (pipettes, boxes and plastics) during the implementation of the tour
5	Product delivery – Guide and Deliverer Component	CBT center is quite beautiful, nonetheless layout of CBT center needs to be tidied up, the Agrocacao needs an aesthetic touch, agrocacao has not been maximized: the tour descriptions need further development and the walk through the cacao farm has not been integrated due to time limitation.
6	Food & Beverage	The lunch and the snack are ok, but food wrappers still use plastic elements, cacao drink is hot besides the air is already hot and the aroma of ginger is not match combined with chocolate.
7	Transportation	The journey from Denpasar is quite far but smooth without traffic congestion
8	Organizing program packages	Good organization, however directions and signage are required at the intersection after entering Pohsanten Village.
9	Price	Need a competitive price
10	Other inputs	Agrocacao tour should be made into a separate package without trekking and not as a part of the Green Living Package

The information presented on Table 2 shows that among the 10 aspects observed and discussed through FGD, it seems that the Existing Green Living Tour Program that had been participated, has too long duration, even though the attraction variety is a plus point but it is inclined to be agricultural in nature, also the agro-cacao is not well presented in the tour program due to the limitation of time. For these reasons, agro-cacao is not recommended to be included in the tour. There is also still an issue of lack of signage and direction on the way to the CBT Center. Feedback is also provided in regard to the material used as a part of the tour program, suggestions are put forward to thoroughly eliminate the use of plastic substance. This feedback needs to be integrated when refining the tour program.

Table 3. FGD Results - Existing Green Living

No	Respondent	Comment
1	FGD Participant 1	Focus on green living, please
2	FGD Participant 2	The trekking is too long
3	FGD Participant 3	The concept of the tour package is very good and fits the nature potency, but the green living lifestyle should also be reflected in the behavior of the surrounding community. For trekking path, consider shortening the distance.
4	FGD Participant 4	Shorten the trekking path
5	FGD Participant 5	More green living activities to make the idea of green living sink in

Apart from the feedback provided earlier, most aspects of the product obtained positive comments. An overall comment was made by one participant who stated that the Green Living Tour Program assists younger generation to understand nature better, even though a note is placed that an understanding should be followed by the implementation of the adopted value in the daily life. These show that the Green Living Tour Program is accepted by the Youth, nonetheless improvements need to be made based on the input given by the tour participants. CBT Pohsanten needs to consider customers' feedback provided by the Tour and FGD participants; in a broader scope, integrating the evaluation of the 5 factors that affect customers' choice: branding, guarantee, environment, service quality, and expectation factor (Prasetia, Sari and Aryana, 2020). These are the 5 aspects in totality that need to be pay attention to and enhanced.

5.2. Results and Discussion of the Modified Green Living Tour

After the refinement and the modification of the Existing Green Living Tour Program; subsequently, the Modified Green Living Tour Program is developed, its content is presented in Figure 4. The adjustment made include: a shortened breeze-walk duration for a more enjoyable walk; the agro-cacao tour component is eliminated as it deviates the focus on the theme of green living; young coconut is served to better suit the theme and guest's need on a hot day; a discussion is added as a last session that allow reflection und understanding of

green living concept to sink deeper; green materials to be used during tour that include sustainable container and cutleries.

To make Green Living Tour a quality product, the program was adjusted based on the analysis results of the research first stage which is the experimentation of the Existing green Living Tour, which was also confirmed and postulated by some researchers. The argument includes: Gee (1990) suggests that time allocation should not be too tight between activities which enables participants to enjoy the tour program; attraction themes should be strong and having high intensity (Arjana, Ernawati, Astawa, 2019).

Table 4. Observation Result - Modified Green Living

No	Aspect	Result
1	Duration	The duration is fit properly, allowing for a leisure stroll and enjoying the scenery along the way while working on the task of drawing leaves and describing their uses.
2	Timing	The timing is appropriate
3	Variety of tourist attraction	Suitable, for non-Hindus can relax and enjoy the scenery at the outer part of the temple while enjoying young coconuts drink.
4	The strength of the attraction theme	Activities focus on sustainable theme and mutually reinforcing
5	Product delivery – Guide and Component	The guide was communicative both in delivering the Green living class and the Breeze-walk
6	Food & Beverage	Already match with the green living concept
7	Transportation	Sufficient and well-arranged transportation
8	Organizing program packages	Well organized, well cared and on time
9	Price	Compete price
10	Other inputs	Consider serving the young coconut in a paper cup or reuse-cup. Suggestion: The final session is followed by a discussion of the results of the assignment "understanding the environment" and a discussion on "green life style".

The green living theme is strengthened by placing sufficient activities related to sustainable living, these for example: green living class, activities for participants that enable a better understanding of plants and trees, the use of environment friendly substances and materials during the tour, green trekking rout with the local guide explaining about sustainable living on the way; agro-cacao as a part of the Green Living Tour Program was eliminated as it caused fraction and make the tour less focus. The Program improvement was conducted, the Modified Green Living Tour was developed and subsequently put into experimentation using these 2 groups, the observation results are presented in Table 4, the FGD result is provided in Table 5, and discussed in the following.

Table 5. FGD Result- Modified Green Living

No	Aspect	Result
1	Duration	The duration was appropriate and made all the participants really enjoy the trip along the trekking route while getting to know the live pharmacy and doing the green assignment more neatly.
2	Timing	Appropriate timing
3	Variety of Tourist Attraction	Sufficient variety of attraction even more emphasizes on the existence of a living pharmacy
4	The Strength of the Attraction Theme	The concept of sustainable is already integrated with tools to support activities, such as the use of leaves as lunch wrappers.
5	Product delivery – Guide and Component Deliverer	Trekking guide is very communicative to participants, resulting in two-way communication which increases understanding and satisfaction on traveling. Furthermore, additional gifts are also provided as a form of appreciation.
6	Food & Beverage	Meets the sustainable concept
7	Transportation	Sufficient and well-organized transportation
8	Organizing program packages	According to the plan

9	Price	Compete price
10	Other inputs	The first input is on the trekking path, which might be shortened again. Second, maintenance needs to be done, especially along the trekking route in the rainy season because the path becomes slippery than usual which is potentially dangerous during the tour.

The Modified green living tour program received positive comments from the participants. Nonetheless, few refinements were also suggested to be made, these for example: arranging signage at the junctions to reach the CBT Center. Adding a discussion at the end of the tour to allow participants to internalise the green living concept was valued.

A general opinion of the participants was requested regarding the Green Living Tour. In general, the aspect of tour enjoyed by the participants are: being together with friends and parents and teachers, taking picture, a little adventure, enjoy the scenery and be close with nature, learning about plant/leaves and its function, praying together, having an exercise, have a walk exploring Pasatan village, study with friends about nature. One participant wrote a very impressive comment: 'My impression after joining this tour is, I am happy to be able to enjoy the tour with CBT Pohsanten Bali because I can learn more about forests and how to protect the environment. I expect that the CBT will continue to develop and be recognised by many people'. These study results confirm the statement expressed by some tourism academicians that community-based tourism is a popular medium for community development (Singh, 2012; Telfer & Sharpley, 2008; Beeton, 2006).

6. Conclusion

Through the steps of the experimentation on the existing and the modified version of Green Living Tour, a suitable Green Living Program for the Youth was identified and formulated. The product is designed for Youth Market Segment. The study output is a solution to two problems: the first one is the problem facing in conserving the forest, and the second is the issue faced by CBT Pohsanten in order to survive the pandemic and still be able to operate in the era of New Normal. CBT Pohsanten can now continue to operate catering the students at Jembrana regency while giving solution to the environment issue.

Limitation and Study forward: Future experimentation on the product is recommended as the formulated Green Living Tour Program is subject to change and modification according to the shift of consumer needs and preferences.

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